

A photograph of a megalithic stone archway. The sun is shining brightly through the opening, creating a lens flare effect. The surrounding landscape is dark and silhouetted, with some trees visible in the background.

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Fourth International Symposium

volume **1**

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On the cover: Markov Kamak Sanctuary in Rila Mountain. Photo by Vasil Markov.

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MEGALITHISM IN CENTRAL PORTUGAL SCENARIOS, SACRED SPACES, RITUALS, DEATH, AND FUNERARY PRACTICES IN RECENT PREHISTORY IN ALTO RIBATEJO

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Abstract. The Alto Ribatejo reveals a complex landscape that facilitated the understanding of the adaptations of prehistoric communities in Portugal. Archaeological evidence reveals the continuity of funerary traditions within cavities and atypical structures alongside the adoption of megalithic architectures. The analysis suggests that the cults and rituals of the Alto Ribatejo communities reflected complex interactions with different domains and subsystems, resulting in a palimpsest of practices and constructive polymorphism.

Keywords: megalithism, caves, atypical monuments

Introduction

Alto Ribatejo, a definition created by Oosterbeek (1994, pp. 78–79), is located north of the middle Tagus River in central Portugal (Fig. 1). Its diverse geomorphology provides a unique opportunity to study the adaptations of recent prehistoric communities in this region, particularly those associated with cults and rituals. We aim to focus primarily on the rituals and beliefs related to burials that occurred during the emergence and full occupation of the megalithic phenomenon.

According to Figure 1, to the right, we can observe the karst landscape, prevalent along the Nabão River, characterized by the presence of limestone terrains, where chemical dissolution processes have given rise to typical formations such as dolines, dry valleys, caves,

and sinkholes. These formations would have provided ancient communities with a series of natural shelters and cavities, used for habitation, as evidenced by the Ave Casta cave (Mateus & Queiróz, 2012), and for ritual and funerary practices, such as the Algar da Água (Figueiredo, 2019b) cavity in Alvaiázere—radiocarbon dating of remains ranges from the end of the 6th millennium BC to the mid-2nd millennium BC (Figueiredo, 2019a), the Cadaval Cave—radiocarbon dating ranges from the end of the 5th millennium BC to the mid-4th millennium BC (Cruz, 1997), the Bone Cave—radiocarbon dating goes from the mid-4th millennium BC to the early 3rd millennium BC (Oosterbeek, 1993; Cruz, 1997), and the Morgado Superior Cave (Tomar)—radiocarbon dating ranges from the 5th millennium BC to the early 3rd millennium BC (Cruz, 2016), or Lapa da Furada (Ourém)—where a single AMS dating places it in the 3rd millennium, just to mention a few (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Geologic map with the representation of region, sites and Nabão and Zêzere River

In contrast, to the left, the rugged terrain along the Zêzere River presents schist landscape, with large overhangs, challenges for human occupation but also offers strategic advantages, such as panoramic views and defensible locations.

Figure 2. Chronologies of archaeological sites. Oxcal calibration

The Tagus River, to the south, is one of the largest rivers in the Iberian Peninsula, flowing across the territory from east to west and acting as a natural communication and mobility route. Not only does it cut through Portugal, but it also served as a bridge between the cultural influences of ancient occupations in the Spanish Extremadura and those of the Portuguese coast. This geomorphological diversity creates a picture of contrasting landscapes and reflects the complexity of human adaptations to different natural environments, cultural processes, and associated structural choices, revealing a rich panorama of cultural variability and adaptive functionality.

Monumental polymorphisms

To understand the cults that flourished in the recent prehistoric period, it is essential to consider the broader landscape and the cultures practices that preceded the construction of the first megalithic architectures. Factors such as the domestication and intensification of resources, settlement patterns, and the inter community dynamics of this period stand out. Furthermore, their economic strategies, cultural influences, social and political structures, as well as spatial organizations, played a fundamental role in this context.

While this article cannot delve into all of these aspects, we have chosen to focus on the funerary rituals and the associated belief behaviors that are evident in Alto Ribatejo.

The Nabão region, characterized by a landscape conducive to the formation of cavities, served as a setting for funerary practices prior to the emergence of megalithism. These cavities represent an intimate interaction with the natural environment, which was not only functional but also central to the symbolic and religious systems of these groups. This bond persisted until the Early/Middle Bronze Age, as indicated by archaeological evidence (Figueiredo, 2021).

In the Zêzere region, where the geomorphology was less conducive to cavity formation, communities adapted their cults and rituals to other elements of the landscape. These communities likely explored rock outcrops or elevations, suggesting a process of symbolic appropriation of the landscape, where natural elements became

incorporated as cultic reference points, replacing or complementing the functions that cavities could serve in neighboring contexts.

This scenario, although not yet fully clarified by archaeology for the Mesolithic or Early Neolithic in the Zêzere area—periods preceding the construction of the first dolmens—becomes evident in later phases, as evidenced by some archaeological finds observed in atypical structures and in proximity to natural rock formations, the Colos Monument (Cruz et al., 2015) and Pedra da Encavalada (Cruz, 2004, 2010, pp. 141–166) are particularly relevant. In the latter site, which is a monument composed of a cluster of monoliths, where it was possible to define organized internal structures with pit burials, the researcher compares to cave burials (idem, 2010, p. 158). The dating of ceramics ($6,082 \pm 620$ BP to $5,999 \pm 697$ BP) places this site chronological prior to dolmen 1 of Vale da Laje (3670 ± 480 BC and 3750 ± 380 BC), found on the other bank located in Zêzere (Cruz, 2010, p. 206) (Fig. 1), and earliest phases of dolmen I and II of Rego da Murta, performed on AMS-human bone, located near the Nabão (Figueiredo, 2019a) (Figure 2).

In the Nabão area, the absence of atypical funerary structures suggests a strong association with the region's natural cavities. Archaeological evidence indicates a gradual transition from individual burials within caves integrated into the Early Neolithic, as observed in Nossa Senhora das Lapas cave (Oosterbeek, 1994), to more complex funerary practices involving multiple individuals interred in pits, sometimes enclosed by stone structures. These behaviors are evident in the caves and megalithic monuments in Nabão (Figueiredo, 2007, 2017, 2019a, 2019b, 2021), as they are presumed for Pedra da Encavalada, near Zêzere, although the author (Cruz, 2010) considers this a site of individual burials due to the site's association with the burial period. At this site, the soil's acidity has prevented the preservation of osteological remains. This makes it difficult to definitively determine the nature of the interments at this location.

The first megalithic architectures appear to have been introduced in the first half of the 4th millennium, likely influenced by southern cultural traditions, based on artifact analogies and the greater antiquity of the dates obtained in these regions. Oosterbeek (1994) proposes an earlier adoption of megalithism near Zêzere, which is in the limestone

area, based on relative comparisons and the presence of macrolithic artifacts in layer D of dolmen Vale da Laje I (Tomar) that may serve as a transitional link between the Mesolithic and the Neolithic (idem, p. 175). However, these objects, are also recorded in later moments in Zêzere (Cruz et al., 2015), and in Nabão, they appear associated with the Copper age phase of Dolmen II of Rego da Murta, in the mid-3rd millennium (Figueiredo, 2007) (Figure 2), and in the final deposits of the dolmen of Azurrague, located in Ourém, which is still undated. In Zêzere, surface records have also been documented at Dolmens 1 and 2 of Vale de Chãos. This suggests a prolonged use of this opportunistic macrolithic industry, of ancient tradition, at least until the end of the 3rd millennium.

Undoubtedly, the earliest chronologies attributed to the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta, the core closest to the cavities of the Nabão River, indicate dates of 4540±30 BP for RMII and 4520±40 BP for RMI, suggesting contemporary deposits and a possible synchronous construction onset, or at least within a very close temporal phase (Figueiredo, 2007, 2017, 2021; Figueiredo et al., 2024). Almost concurrently, the occupation of Algar da Água, a cavity a few kilometers from this complex, is recorded with a dating of 4440±30 BP (Figueiredo, 2019b), and of Lapa da Furada in Ourém, dated at 4149±33 BP, both cases based on samples of human bones (table1).

However, the known megalithic monuments in the karst area are scarce, which seems to be more related to the lack of rigorous archaeological surveys than to a supposed absence of cultic practices. In the region, besides the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta, composed of 14 archaeological sites, including dolmens, menhirs (Figueiredo, 2013), sites with rock art (cup marks), and other structures (Figueiredo, 2021, pp. 38–50), we also find the Azurrague dolmen in Ourém, further south and closer to the coast (Fig. 1). Near Rego da Murta, the menhir group of Quinta do Paço was recorded, accompanied by materials associating it with the 3rd–2nd millennium BC (Figure 2). While these are the only known remnants currently, historical reports suggest that other similar structures once existed in Alvaiázere but have since been destroyed. Additionally, place names like Vale de Antas in Ourém (meaning Valley of Dolmens), suggest the potential for more

megalithic sites in the region, reinforcing the need for further archaeological investigations. Asserting a scarcity of megalithic monuments in the region, known for its caves, seems imprecise to us.

Issues and interpretations

To understand the impact of megalithism in the region, its symbolic concepts, and functionalities, it is crucial to examine the areas closest to the cavities. In the Alto Ribatejo region, the introduction of new cultures and beliefs did not completely replace traditional practices; instead, it allowed them to coexist with preexisting ritual behaviors, extending at least until the Middle Bronze Age. This situation is evident at Algar da Água, a cavity that shows evidence of funerary cults dating from 6200 ±30 BP to at least 3200 ±30 BP, as well as in the megalithic monument of Rego da Murta I (Figueiredo, 2019a), where dates extend up to 3510 ±40 BP (Figure 2). These sites, which are less than 8 km apart, along with dolmen II of Rego da Murta, are key locations for understanding behaviors in Alto Nabão today. The contemporaneous use of cavities near megalithic monuments is also evident in the Lapa da Furada cave, where the previously mentioned dating places it at the peak of dolmen usage, located less than 2 km from the dolmen of Azurrague. This raises the question of why funerary traditions continued alongside these megalithic practices.

Throughout the megalithic phase, evidence indicates a complex framework of interactions, symbolism, structural dynamics, and functions that are still being explored by archaeology. Separating the sacred from the profane—particularly outside the cavities and even in understanding the dolmens—is complex. Many acts and concepts remained deeply rooted in social and political systems, influencing various aspects of daily and communal life.

The idea that megalithic structures were not merely places of worship or burial, but central points in the social, political, and symbolic lives of prehistoric communities, has been widely discussed (Cunliffe, 1998; Chippindale & Gill, 1997; Bradley, 1998; Tilley, 1994; Fowler, 2004; Scarre, 2002). These monuments represented more than just ritual

spaces: they were symbols of power and identity, reinforcing the bond between communities and their territory.

The construction of these structures required significant collective effort, involving the mobilization of resources and social organization, suggesting a close relationship between ritual practices and political control. In the case of the dolmen of Rego da Murta II, the collective deposits in pits contemporary with those observed in the Gruta dos Ossos in Tomar (Figueiredo, 2007, pp. 130–148) indicate a continuity of beliefs between natural spaces and megalithic monuments, associating the same belief system and likely the same social group. Without a change in ritual, the functional symbolic process of adopting megalithic architectures would likely have been related to other propositions, probably to legitimize the authority of specific groups over a space. The positioning of monuments in flow areas—such as rivers and routes of mobility—suggests a role in demarcating territory, creating alliances between groups or establishing borders. This intertwining of the sacred with the profane is also manifested in the choices of monument locations, in spatial orientation, and the very architecture of the structures, which reflect both a religious function and an expression of social and territorial organization (Figueiredo, 2007; Figueiredo et al., 2018). Therefore, understanding megalithism and the rituals associated with it requires a holistic approach that recognizes the complex interconnection between religious practices, political structure, and territorial dominance strategies.

Megalithic structures, with their monumental characteristic of enduring over time, introduced unprecedented forms of religious and social expression, potentially altering the dynamics of the communities that adopted them. In this context, the adoption of new practices did not occur immediately or in a decontextualized manner. According to Bourdieu (1977), for an action to become valid and structuring within a community, the underlying structure of that action must, in turn, become part of the society's system of practices. In other words, a practice is only truly adopted when it is internalized and integrated into the group's habits and behaviors, shaping its way of life and worldview. Megalithism, as a collective expression that required strong community adherence, would have had to demonstrate its advantages in both the

sacred and the profane. Rather than simply replacing traditional practices, it became intertwined with local traditions.

It is believed that this is what occurred in the central region of Portugal, where a culturally hybrid environment emerged, with ancient rituals continuing to be practiced—perhaps adapted to the new contexts provided by megalithic structures, as seems to be the case with Pedra da Encavalada, near the Zêzere River. The adoption of megalithism might have been partial or selective, with communities incorporating only certain aspects of this new tradition while maintaining other practices they deemed essential to their cultural identity. This selective adherence may have resulted from the perception that the immediate benefits of megalithic practices did not outweigh the significant effort and time required for their implementation. In other words, the high cost in terms of resources and labor to build megalithic monuments, combined with the absence of some traditional symbolic elements, may not have yielded a sufficiently positive impact, leading to slower adoption or the combination of new practices with already established traditions.

This coexistence of traditions suggests that, rather than a simple cultural evolution or replacement, earlier ritualistic practices and those performed at megalithic monuments could have followed parallel paths, each with its own symbolic and functional logic. Cave rituals, with their ancestral roots, may have been guided by an understanding of space and spirituality linked to the intimacy and isolation of natural cavities, representing a more conservative connection to past behaviors. Similarly, associations with natural landscape features, such as rocky outcrops observed particularly in the Zêzere region, with datings placing them in synchrony with megalithism, could be remnants of these ancient traditions that continued to hold significance for the community.

Megalithic monuments, erected in open spaces, might have symbolized another form of interaction with the sacred and the social. Perhaps more public and communal, they may have reflected changes in social structures or perceptions of ritual space and ownership. This transition coincides with a cosmological transformation observed during the Neolithic period when humans began to perceive and interact with the landscape in new ways. As hunter-gatherers became producers, their economic ties to the land deepened. This process of domesticating the

natural environment—encompassing agriculture, animal husbandry, and living spaces—promoted increasing anthropization of the landscape. Through megalithic monuments—marks and signs left on the land—space began to be shaped not only for productive purposes but also as a symbolic expression of power and control.

Thus, while caves represented a more introspective and conservative connection to the past, megalithic monuments appear to have served as expressions of a new social order, where power and identity were negotiated in public, visible spaces. These monuments reflected a broader sense of belonging and territorial assertion.

This analogy was already raised in 2007 (Figueiredo, 2007) in the analysis of the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta, where it is argued that the monuments are closely linked to the space they occupy as a result of a careful process of appropriation and interaction with the landscape. The deliberate placement of menhirs in relation to the dolmens in this complex—where at least seven isolated monoliths were recorded around them—and the specific design and orientation of the dolmen corridors (Figueiredo et al., 2018) are understood as intentional. This suggests a profound symbolic and functional connection with the surrounding environment.

The construction of the dolmens required meticulous planning. Before erecting the vertical supports and building the monument, small blocks were placed on the ground as reference points. Following this, records from the same site reveal the execution of a cremation deposit, connecting the ancestors with the foundation of the site and linking the monument to the community. Only after the supports were in place and the monument was fully constructed were the first ritual acts performed inside. This approach highlights the importance that these prehistoric societies attributed to the relationship between monuments and the landscape, which may have also included the sky within their cosmological system, considering it a determining factor for positioning and spatial orientation (Figueiredo et al., 2018).

It has also been argued that the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta is located in a strategic crossing zone along the Rego da Murta stream, a significant tributary of the Nabão River (Figueiredo, 2021). This area has been defined as an optimal mobility zone, as

geomorphological evidence indicates that its characteristics facilitate the movement and circulation of contemporary communities traveling between the north and south. It is further suggested that this optimal mobility may have influenced the choice for constructing the Roman road (*idem*, 2017), which, in a later phase, connected Selium (present-day Tomar) to Conimbriga, passing through areas adjacent to the prehistoric core.

The strategic positioning of these monuments also finds parallels in other contexts, such as the Bronze Age burial mounds in the municipality of Abrantes, located near the Zêzere River. These structures align with the course of an ancient route of mobility, even though the exact chronology of this route remains uncertain (Batista & Gaspar, 2007). The relevance of this mobility factor was also observed in Ana Rosa Cruz's postdoctoral research (2020) during the investigation of Mamoa 1 do Souto and other contemporary tumuli, such as Mamoa de Porto Escuro, which are distributed along festo lines in the Abrantes region (Cruz, 2010, 2020, pp. 12–14). This evidence suggests a function associated with the mobility and circulation of communities, consolidating a central role in territorial and social control.

Final considerations

The continuity of rituals performed in natural cavities, such as the Algar da Água, which presents funerary traces from the Early Neolithic to the Middle Bronze Age, and examples like Gruta dos Ossos, Morgado Superior, and Lapa da Furada, with datings from the Copper Age, demonstrate the resilience of ancient funerary traditions, even after the diffusion of megalithism.

In regions where natural cavities are absent, the maintenance of such practices is observed through associations with atypical structures. Examples include the Monument of Colos (Gaspar & Batista, 2000; Cruz et al., 2015) and Pedra Encavalada (Cruz, 2004, 2020), which reveal a high degree of structural polymorphism throughout these periods. Pedra Encavalada, located in the core of Jogada, integrates into a space occupied by megalithic dolmens, possibly sharing the same sacred space given the collective nature of the core.

In the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta, Alvaiázere, the entire surrounding area has been interpreted as a symbolic-religious space. This is suggested by the presence of material traces, mainly chert and quartzite chips and cores, distributed in an intentional spatial pattern, as well as by the apparent organization in the positioning of the monuments. A similar situation, albeit less evident, can be considered for the cores of Jogada and Vale do Chãos, in Abrantes, near the Zêzere River, or even for the space integrating the Azurrague dolmen, excavated in 2024, where a possible menhir and a set of cores and flakes were also found scattered around.

The diversity observed in these practices suggests that the prehistoric communities of central Portugal integrated megalithism in a flexible manner, inserting it into a dynamic and adaptable ritual panorama clearly resulting from an importation. This process of cultural assimilation and adaptation highlights the complexity of interactions between new cultural influences and established traditions. Moreover, it indicates that the ritual landscapes of the region were shaped by various factors, including local geography and the symbolic and social needs of the communities.

The study of these cultural transitions is essential for understanding the complexity of change and the resilience of local traditions in the face of external influences. Symbols and ritual practices of the past were not completely abandoned; rather, they coexisted with new ritual forms, resulting in a multifaceted symbolic landscape where different conceptions of the sacred and ritual space cohabited and interacted in diverse ways. The analytical challenge lies in determining whether these variations reflect the coexistence of distinct cultural groups or a gradual evolution of practices within the same group, adapting to different spatial and temporal contexts.

This fragmented and multifaceted scenario creates fertile ground for academic debate, as researchers must reconcile evidence that may initially seem contradictory or incompatible. The discussion intensifies as new archaeological findings are incorporated into the corpus of evidence, requiring constant revisions and re-evaluations of existing theories.

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